

Emerging methods and applications of ultra-high field MR spectroscopic imaging in the human brain

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ABSTRACT

Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopic Imaging (MRSI) of the brain enables insights into the metabolic changes and fluxes in diseases such as tumors, multiple sclerosis, epilepsy, or hepatic encephalopathy, as well as insights into general brain functionality. However, the routine application of MRSI is mostly hampered by very low signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) due to the low concentrations of metabolites, about 10000 times lower than water. Furthermore, MRSI spectra have a dense information content with many overlapping metabolite resonances, especially for proton MRSI. MRI scanners at ultra-high field strengths, like 7 T or above, offer the opportunity to increase SNR, as well as the separation between resonances, thus promising to solve both challenges. Yet, MRSI at ultra-high field strengths is challenged by decreased B₀- and B₁-homogeneity, shorter T₂ relaxation times, stronger chemical shift displacement errors, and aggravated lipid contamination. Therefore, to capitalize on the advantages of ultra-high field strengths, these challenges must be overcome. This review focuses on the challenges MRSI of the human brain faces at ultra-high field strength, as well as the possible applications to this date.

1. Introduction

Magnetic resonance spectroscopic imaging (MRSI) is a versatile tool for imaging the dynamics and steady-state concentrations of metabolic compounds [1]. Rather than imaging proton density and T₁/T₂-relaxation times, the goal of MRSI is to image chemical compounds containing hydrogen or other nuclei, such as phosphorus. All MRSI techniques have in common that they extend the encoding of the up to three spatial dimensions known from conventional MRI techniques to that of a resonance frequency-specific axis as used in single-voxel MR spectroscopy (MRS). The latter allows the signals of several different chemical compounds in the obtained MR spectra to be separated and quantified simultaneously. This makes MRSI a powerful imaging tool to study biochemistry, including characteristic spatial and temporal patterns in the human body non-invasively and *in vivo*. The quality of MR spectra is generally determined by three main parameters: 1) a high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), which is required to separate the signal of interest from random fluctuations; 2) a high spectral resolution, which is required to separate the signals in a spectrum from each other reliably;

and 3) the presence of unwanted nuisance signal contributions, which should be reduced to avoid biases in the quantification of target metabolite levels [2].

However, the concentrations of metabolites in tissue are generally quite low (on the order of mM), in contrast to the signal of protons in water molecules (~10000-times larger), which reduces the obtainable SNR [3,4]. In addition, *in vivo* MRSI also faces several subject-dependent nuisances, such as spatial field inhomogeneities and temporal scanner/subject-related instabilities, which lowers the spectral resolution [4]. Both, the relatively low SNR and the limited spectral resolution impose limitations on the quality of *in vivo* MRSI when compared to high-resolution NMR experiments.

MR scanners with an ultra-high static magnetic field (UHF) can partially alleviate these limitations. Like all conventional MRI techniques, MRSI benefits from a significant increase in sensitivity and SNR at higher static magnetic field strengths (B₀) [5]. Furthermore, the Larmor frequencies of all metabolite signals increase, hence their frequency dispersion increases, while the signal linewidth is typically not increased by the same amount. In addition, both the spectral separation and the SNR benefit from a strong simplification of the spectral patterns,

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Abbreviations

2HG	2-hydroxyglutarate	MS	multiple sclerosis
BPD	Bipolar disorder	NMR	nuclear magnetic resonance
CSDE	chemical shift displacement error	OVS	outer volume suppression
EPI	echo planar imaging	pTx	parallel transmission
EPSI	echo planar spectroscopic imaging	RF	radio frequency
FID	free induction decay	SAR	specific absorption rate
FIDLOVS	FID acquisition localized with outer volume suppression	SNR	signal-to-noise ratio
FWHM	full width at half maximum	SPICE	spectroscopic imaging by exploiting spatio-spectral correlation
Glu	glutamate	tCho	total Choline;
Gln	glutamine;	tCr	total Creatine;
Glx	glutamate + glutamine;	TE	echo time;
GM	grey matter	tNAA	total N-Acetyl Aspartate
MDD	major depression disorders	TR	repetition time;
MRS	magnetic resonance spectroscopy	UHF	ultra-high static magnetic field
MRSI	magnetic resonance spectroscopic imaging	WM	white matter

which results in higher, and more narrow spectral peaks. In this manner, signals like gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), glutamine separated from glutamate, or glycine separated from *myo*-Inositol, which are difficult to quantify at lower field strengths with MRSI, can be estimated more easily with UHF. This opens up prospects for the quantification of important new biomarkers in diseases such as cancer [6], multiple sclerosis [7], epilepsy [8], or hepatic encephalopathy [9], as well as in psychiatric disorders or neuroscience.

Consequently, MRSI has significantly benefited from the ever increasing B0 of human whole-body MR scanners, which has currently reached 10.5T, with new installations targeting even higher B0s such as 11.7 T [10]. Real proliferation has happened with 7T scanners over the last decade, driven by the introduction of the first clinically-approved models [11–13]. While the exact number of 7 T installations is difficult to track, there are currently at least over 70 such sites worldwide [14].

Despite the obvious benefits of UHF, the development of MRSI at UHF was relatively slow (especially for ¹H-MRSI), because it was dramatically outperformed by similar developments in single-voxel MRS techniques. While single-voxel MRS and MRSI share many common challenges at UHF, including those related to accurate spatial localization, shorter T2-relaxation times, field inhomogeneities, nuisance signal, and temporal instabilities [15], these effects pose typically even stronger limitations on MRSI. Also, encoding up to four dimensions simultaneously can result in large amounts of raw data and time-consuming data acquisition and processing, which has particularly slowed the rise of ¹H-MRSI at UHF [16]. Therefore, fully automatic spectral quantification and automatic quality control are necessary to handle such large data sets.

Historically, despite numerous potential applications, from cancer diagnostics to basic neuroscience, MRSI has been hampered by limitations such as scan time, resolution, and reproducibility compared to MRI, and is only sparingly used in clinical practice [4]. Nevertheless, both recent advances in MRSI methodology and the recent clinical certification of 7 T MRI have raised expectations that UHF MRSI methods will reach a more widespread use in biomedical research and clinical applications in the near future. This review explores the technical developments and applications of human brain UHF MRSI since the availability of human UHF imagers. In order to focus on UHF technologies, we will not cover general processing or the quantification methodology available at all field strengths nor general machine-learning implementations in this review.

2. Methods - challenges and solutions

As mentioned previously, UHF MRSI inherently faces challenges that make the acquisition of a perfect spectral data set difficult, including the decreased homogeneity of both B0 and the RF field (B1), increased SAR and thus limited B1 amplitudes, the intrinsically shorter T2 relaxation times, the stronger chemical shift displacement errors and lipid artifacts, the typically long measurement times, and the need for automatic processing and quality assurance tools due to the usually higher resolutions. Although lipid artifacts and long measurement times are not specific to UHF MRSI, we believe that they deserve to be covered here because the respective problem is either aggravated (in the case of lipids) or can be remedied (in the case of the measurement times, due to the abundance of SNR) at UHF. This chapter focuses on the problems typically faced when performing UHF MRSI and presents some solutions that have been suggested recently.

2.1. Basics of MRSI acquisition

Single-voxel MRS is a versatile tool to non-invasively probe the biochemical composition of tissue from a cuboid volume. In contrast to MRS, MRSI provides spectral information from several spatial locations. Traditional MRSI uses phase encoding, in addition to volume pre-selection (e.g. PRESS, STEAM, (semi)LASER) to provide localization of each spectrum. Unfortunately, this results in very long measurement times, since only a single phase encoding step is usually acquired per repetition time (TR), and the necessary phase encoding steps increase strongly with the resolution, especially in 3D. Additionally, volume pre-selection provides useful spectra only from within a certain rectangular box, which is especially challenging if lesions are located at the border of the brain. In the recent decades, these and other challenges have been overcome, as will be shown in the following subchapters.

2.2. B0 homogeneity

One of the biggest advantages of UHF for MRSI is the reduced linewidth in ppm due to the higher spectral dispersion. However, this reduction in linewidth is compromised by a decreased B0 homogeneity. As a consequence, the resulting final linewidth can be the same or even worse than at lower field strengths, depending on the B0 homogeneity. Thus, to capitalize on the reduced linewidth of UHF MRSI, the B0 inhomogeneity must be addressed.

An intuitive way to improve B0 homogeneity is the addition of higher-order spherical harmonic terms beyond the standard second- to third-order harmonic terms of current MR scanners. This has been

shown to improve B0 uniformity of various brain regions, resulting in decreased linewidths and increased SNRs at UHF [17–20]. Spherical harmonics are orthogonal basis functions, and therefore, each term can be optimized independently, leading to a very simple consecutive optimization. However, the coils to produce spherical harmonics are typically large, and therefore, need expensive amplifiers, cause strong Eddy-currents, and cannot be switched rapidly.

Local shim coil arrays drop the orthogonality requirement in favor of an increased freedom in design, smaller eddy currents, faster switching times, and lower-cost amplifiers. They use small, local shim coils that are applied in addition to the vendor-provided 2nd-3rd order spherical harmonic shims, and are most effective at improving the field

homogeneity near the surface of the brain [21]. Such systems can be designed as a shim coil insert [21,22], or as radio frequency (RF) coils for simultaneous RF reception and shimming [20,23]. Local shim coil arrays have been shown to provide similar B0 homogeneities as 3rd or 4th order spherical harmonic terms while decreasing the presence of eddy currents, allowing for faster switching times, as well as being more cost effective [20,22,24]. Their main drawback is that they are in competition with the RF coils with regard to the available space close to the subject's head. An example of the benefits a local array shim provides for MRSI vs. spherical harmonics is given in Fig. 1.

Spherical harmonic, as well as local shim coils, can be used for dynamic shimming, i.e., the shim settings can be adjusted during the

Fig. 1. Anatomical reference (top row), total N-acetylaspartate (tNAA) and SNR maps (2nd row), total Creatine (tCr) and tCr Cramér–Rao lower bound (CRLB) maps (3rd row), total choline (tCho) and full width at half maximum (FWHM) maps (4th row), together with the B0 maps (5th row), and three sample spectra for the scanner second-order spherical harmonics shim ($2SH_{box}$) vs. a local shim array in addition to the second-order spherical harmonics shim ($2SH_{box} + AC/DC_{brain}$). Using the local shim array clearly improves the metabolic maps in the frontal area, decreases the tCr CRLBs and FWHM, and improves the B0 homogeneity. The data were acquired at a 7 T Magnetom scanner (Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen, Germany). Figure provided with kind permission of Morteza Esmaeili.

measurement. This process mainly benefits the sequential acquisition of different volumes in multi-slice sequences. In practice, dynamic third-order spherical harmonic shims, which are applied during an echo planar imaging (EPI) sequence, can reduce the B0 inhomogeneity over the whole brain compared to a static global shim [24]. In 2020, Boer et al. used dynamic shimming to dynamically switch between a shim for EPI and a shim for MRS, benefitting the quality of both acquisitions. Arango et al. showed at 3T that dynamically switching between a shim optimized for lipid inversion and a shim for metabolite detection can improve lipid suppression and spectral linewidth at the same time [25]. Yet, as far as we are aware, there are no publications about dynamic shimming in MRSI at UHF at this point, perhaps owing to the fact that dynamic shimming to achieve high B0 homogeneity is restricted to multi-slice acquisitions, which are rarely done in MRSI at UHF.

A completely different approach to mitigate the detrimental B0 effects solely during reconstruction was proposed by Kirchner et al., who suggested upsampling the MRSI data to the resolution of an auxiliary B0 map, performing a correction based on the B0 field, and subsequently downsampling to the original size [26]. This process was proposed to decrease spectral linewidth and increase SNR; however, thus far, there is no evidence that those technical improvements had a measurable effect on spectral fitting performance or the resulting metabolite maps.

In summary, B0 inhomogeneity is one of the biggest challenges at UHF. It can be partially solved by using higher spherical harmonic terms, local shim coils, dynamic shimming, or post-processing. However, none of these methods have been able to provide an ideally homogeneous B0 field, which would be necessary for whole-brain MRSI at UHF. It is also worth mentioning that subject motion may strongly deteriorate the B0-homogeneity achieved by advanced shimming methods [24,27], since spatially very complex shim fields can diverge rather quickly outside of the shim volume. Thus, very wrong fields may be applied after subject motion. However, some methods like local shim array coils could be able to dynamically adapt for changes caused by subject motion, as their shim currents can be switched very rapidly. Yet, to the best of our knowledge, this has not been shown so far.

2.3. B1 homogeneity

At UHF, the RF wavelength approaches the anatomical dimensions, which results in a reduced B1 homogeneity [28]. Strong B1 inhomogeneities can severely reduce the SNR and thereby deteriorate one of the main advantages of UHF, which warrants the development of strategies to reduce B1 inhomogeneity or its effects. At clinical field-strengths, B1 inhomogeneity effects are significantly less pronounced and, also, the lower specific absorption rate (SAR) values of RF pulses at lower field-strengths permit the use of adiabatic pulses more easily.

Adiabatic pulses do not improve the B1 homogeneity itself, but mitigate the B1-induced problems by making the RF pulses less B1-sensitive. They achieve this by slowly rotating the effective B1 field toward the desired flip angle so that the magnetization follows the applied effective B1, resulting in a reduced sensitivity to B1 inhomogeneities at the cost of higher SAR, B1 amplitudes, and pulse durations, and hence longer minimum TEs. Many pulse sequences common in UHF MRSI, like LASER, SPECIAL, or semi-LASER, use adiabatic pulses [29–31].

Another way to improve the B1 inhomogeneity is to use multiple RF coils for parallel transmission (pTx). In this manner, any conceivable excitation profile can be approximated, e.g., a uniform profile [32]. However, creating an RF pulse in this way requires specialized hardware, software, calibration scans, and sophisticated algorithms. The latter two requirements might be circumvented by universal pulses [33]. An easier alternative is to use a fixed pulse shape and only change the pulse's amplitude and phase [34–38]. pTx has been used for UHF only by Patel et al. for MRSI [39], and by He et al. for MRS [40].

Another interesting approach toward improving the B1 field

homogeneity consists of the addition of passive dielectric elements close to the measured object. These elements have a very high dielectric constant, and thus, influence the B1 field in their vicinity. If placed appropriately, they can homogenize the B1 field, resulting in improved image quality and SAR values, which was first shown numerically in 2001 [41]. Furthermore, dielectric elements were simulated and experimentally tested in 2012, resulting in recommendations for permittivity and thickness [42]. Various different materials were suggested, ranging from metal titanates [43] to aqueous-based perovskite suspensions [44], and, most recently, artificial dielectric pads consisting of stacked capacitive grids [45].

2.4. Water contamination

The water concentration is about 10^4 times higher than that of metabolites, and thus the water peaks dominates ^1H -MRS(I) spectra. Without water-suppression or water-removal in post-processing, the metabolites of interest can usually not be quantified, and strong side bands caused by mechanical vibrations of the gradient system may be present in the spectral range of interest [46]. Thus, water suppression is usually performed with methods like variable pulse power and optimized relaxation delays (VAPOR) [47], or water suppression enhanced through T1 effects (WET) [48]. At UHF, water suppression is challenged by strong B0- and B1-inhomogeneities, thus either shifting the water peak out of the water-suppression pulse frequency range, or applying wrong flip angles to the water signal. To remedy the B1-inhomogeneity issue, pulses less sensitive to B1 inhomogeneities can be used, as demonstrated by Ma et al., who managed to achieve an overall 57% reduction of the residual water peaks [49].

2.5. Shorter T2s

The T2 relaxation times, as well as the T2* values, have been shown to decrease with field strengths, and are thus substantially shorter at UHF [50], resulting in very rapid signal decay. To overcome this problem, the used echo times (TE) are usually shortened, often below 30 ms. Alternatively, the TE can be reduced even further by acquiring the free induction decay (FID) signal—which can be done almost immediately after the excitation—rather than generating and waiting for the spin echo. FID-MRSI can have an acquisition delay as low as 1.3 ms [51]. Methods with many refocusing pulses, such as LASER, are suboptimal at UHF because they cannot easily achieve sufficiently short echo times.

2.6. Chemical shift displacement error

Due to the fact that in a magnetic gradient field, spatial locations correspond to resonance frequencies, the images of metabolites with different resonance frequencies are spatially shifted. This phenomenon is referred to as chemical shift displacement error (CSDE) and it presents a challenge in MRS. The magnitude of the CSDE increases with B0 due to the proportional frequency dispersion. To overcome this problem, the gradient strength during excitation/refocusing must be increased, requiring shortened RF durations, and thus, increased RF power for conventional RF pulses. The CSDE can also be reduced by broadband, adiabatic RF pulses, however, at the cost of increased SAR. Thus, excitation schemes (partially) using adiabatic pulses, such as SPECIAL, LASER, semiLASER, or schemes that avoid refocusing pulses, such as FID acquisitions, are recommended at UHF instead of PRESS or STEAM [52].

2.7. Lipid contamination

Although lipid signals are also a problem at clinical field-strengths, they pose an even greater challenge at UHF due to the typically shorter TEs, stronger CSDEs, and worse B0 homogeneity, requiring special care when handling lipid signals.

One of the most common ways to handle lipid signals is by volume

pre-selection or outer volume suppression (OVS). OVS spoils the signal after excitation in rectangular OVS slabs, placed manually around the brain, while volume pre-selection only excites and refocuses signals from a rectangular box, usually excluding the scalp, using acquisition schemes such as PRESS, LASER, or sLASER. Both methods work well for lipid suppression, but increase SAR, and thus, the minimum feasible TR, and using these methods signals from brain regions close to the scalp cannot be acquired, the minimum TE is increased (volume pre-selection), or the preparation time increases due to manually placing the OVS slabs (OVS). Especially at UHF, the increased TE and SAR are problematic due to the shorter T2* relaxation times and increased SAR demands. Therefore, they are used less frequently at UHF, but are still very common [53–58].

A hardware-related solution to reduce lipid contamination is the crusher coil. Crusher coils are capable of generating a highly inhomogeneous, superficial magnetic field through the application of a short pulse [59]. This field can effectively dephase the magnetization of lipids near the coils, offering an effective and simple form of lipid suppression while minimizing the effects on signals in the brain. Yet, a tradeoff between efficient lipid suppression and avoiding alterations of the brain signal may be difficult to achieve. Recently, crusher coils were applied to 7 T FID-MRSI in 2017 by Ma et al., and, in 2020, Bhogal et al. implemented crusher coils for measuring metabolite concentrations of central brain structures [49,60].

The detrimental effects of lipid signals can also be reduced by focusing on the shimming of the scalp layer. By defining an additional shim region to restrict the B0 inhomogeneities in the scalp, the lipid signals are less likely to overlap with the metabolite range [61]. Another approach is to use AC/DC coils to produce B0 modulations that maximize the frequency dispersion between lipids and metabolite signals during a lipid attenuation module, thus increasing the efficiency of that module [25].

A sequence-related solution is T1-based lipid nulling, which relies on the fact that lipid resonances have much shorter T1-relaxation times than metabolites. The lipid signal will thus relax faster after one or several inversion pulses, which can be exploited to reduce the lipid signals, while the metabolite signals are reduced only slightly [62–64]. The inversion can even be applied to the main lipid resonance frequency selectively, but this is problematic due to the strong B0 inhomogeneities at UHF.

Two purely post-processing-based lipid removal methods are the Hankel singular value decomposition [65], and the lipid regularized reconstruction [66,67]. The first decomposes the measured spectrum into a specified number of Lorentzian signals with different frequencies and damping factors, but has been shown to struggle if strong Gaussian components comprise the signals [68]. The lipid-regularized reconstruction is based on the fact that lipid signals are spatially and spectrally orthogonal to metabolite signals. The spatial orthogonality is used to find a set of lipid basis vectors from the scalp layer, where no metabolite signals are present. The spectral orthogonality is exploited by penalizing the projection of the lipid basis vectors onto the reconstructed metabolite spectra. This method has become popular in recent years at clinical field-strengths [69,70], and for UHF [71–73]. Yet, the process may alter the measured metabolite concentrations inside the brain compared to the unregularized data [74].

2.8. Long acquisition times

Long acquisition times are a general problem with MRSI, but UHF offers an abundance of SNR for some applications. This high reconstruction fidelity can be traded against acquisition speed using several acceleration methods, which will be described here.

Parallel imaging uses the intrinsic signal localization of the different array coil channels to reconstruct images with aliasing due to regular k-space undersampling. The un-aliasing can be done in k-space (GRAPPA) [75] or in the image-domain (SENSE) [76]. An advantage in MRSI

compared to MRI is that the acquisition time of image-based sensitivity maps or auto-calibration signals are negligible compared to the MRSI acquisition. However, MRSI also faces more challenges due to the large voxel size [77], or overwhelming lipid signals. In UHF MRSI, parallel imaging has been used extensively [73,78–82] and benefits especially from the more localized sensitivities of array coils [83].

Compressed sensing relies on the fact that the acquisition can be accelerated by random undersampling if data are compressible. Although this causes noise-like artifacts with traditional reconstructions, the underlying signal can be recovered when using a non-linear, iterative reconstruction that exploits the signal sparsity signal in a transform domain [84]. Compressed sensing benefits greatly from more dimensions, e.g., the additional time dimension in MRSI. However, only one study undersampled along the time domain in ¹H-MRSI due to the spectral artifacts that can be caused by the overwhelmingly large water and lipid signals [85], while others have undersampled only in k-space [69,86–88]. At UHF, compressed sensing has been sparsely used for MRSI [86].

Spatiospectral encoding is another very common acceleration method in MRSI. By applying a gradient waveform during data acquisition, several k-space points can be acquired instead of only one as in phase encoding. These gradient waveforms are then repeated with a frequency on the order of 1 kHz (depending on the desired spectral bandwidth) to acquire spectral information. Common gradient waveforms are k-space lines (echo-planar spectroscopic imaging (EPSI)) [89, 90], spirals [91], rosettes [92], and concentric rings [93]. At UHF, the required spectral bandwidths are so high that some trajectories can become SNR-inefficient or have limited spatial resolution. Nevertheless, spatio-spectral encoding is the most common acceleration method at clinical field-strengths, and has been used extensively at UHF [23,56,58, 94–96]. Fig. 2 shows an example of how spatio-spectral encoding can be utilized to achieve high spatial and spectral resolution simultaneously, for example, by separating glutamate (Glu) and glutamine (Gln). The individual mapping of Gln instead of their sum (Glx) is important for diseases such as brain tumors, hepatic encephalopathy, and edemas, in general.

Low-rank approximations can be used to accelerate MRSI or to improve the reconstruction fidelity by denoising the signal. The basis of these methods is that B0-corrected, nuisance-free, noiseless MRSI data is rank-deficient. Because noisy MRSI data has full rank, a low-rank approximation can be used to discriminate between signal and noise, and thereby denoise the data. Moreover, as a result of the rank-deficiency, the data can be written as a product of a small set of spatial and temporal basis functions. The temporal basis functions can be estimated from a low-resolution MRSI data set, while the spatial basis functions are estimated from a temporally undersampled, high-resolution data set. Since both datasets can be acquired quickly, this is usually faster than acquiring one high-resolution, fully-sampled dataset. Low-rank approximations have been used in a few publications at clinical field-strengths [97–101], but have been published only in the form of conference abstracts for UHF [102,103]. At UHF, especially, the stronger B0 inhomogeneity and stronger nuisance signals can pose a problem since both increase the rank.

2.9. Summary of challenges and solutions

In summary, MRSI at UHF offers many opportunities and advantages over clinical field-strengths, but some challenges still must be overcome. The decreased B0 homogeneity is one of the biggest challenges, and although quite some effort has been put into solving this, MRSI at locations close to air cavities is still not feasible at UHF, thus prohibiting whole-brain MRSI. Furthermore, as long as these solutions are not integrated routinely into clinical or research scanners, the scope of the developed methods is limited. Lipid contamination is another big challenge for MRSI, in general, but is often aggravated at UHF because of typically shorter TEs and the less-frequent use of volume preselection

Fig. 2. Transversal, sagittal, and coronal views of anatomical images, Glu, Gln, Glu CRLB values, and Gln CRLB values, together with the B0 map (bottom left) and a sample spectrum (bottom right). The Glu and Gln maps show a strong contrast between grey matter (GM) and white matter (WM) and an excellent spectral separation, as depicted by the spectrum taken from the location indicated by the red arrow. Data were acquired with a nominal resolution was $2.75 \times 2.75 \times 2.75 \text{ mm}^3$ with an acquisition time of 15:11 min:s at a 7 T Magnetom scanner (Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen, Germany). Reproduced from Hingerl et al., 2020 [16] with permission from *Investigative Radiology*. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

and OVS. To date, no developed method is capable of solving this challenge effectively for problematic acquisitions, e.g., with very short TEs and without volume preselection. Although the other challenges, i. e., B1 inhomogeneities, short T2s, CSDEs, and long acquisition times, pose their own difficulties, they have been overcome to a large degree in recent years.

In contrast to human MRS(I), higher field strengths are typically available in pre-clinical MRS(I), e.g. 9.4 T and above [104]. Furthermore, gradient strength and slew rate, SAR, and time constraints are usually more relaxed in comparison to human MRS(I). Thus, the achievable, but also the necessary resolutions are higher, up to about $0.75 \times 0.75 \times 1.1 \text{ mm}^3$ for 1H-MRSI [105]. Due to the relaxed time constraints, acceleration methods play less of a role in preclinical MRSI, which is why phase encoded MRSI and single-voxel MRS are often used. With smaller voxels or volumes of interest, B0-inhomogeneity is typically less of a problem, and together with the usually higher field strengths, this results in a much better spectral separation. Consequently, metabolites such as GABA, Glu, Gln, or NAAG can be more readily quantified. In addition, due to the higher sensitivity and often longer measurement times, X-nuclear MRS(I) like ^{31}P -, ^{13}C - or hyperpolarized ^{13}C -MRSI are more prominent in preclinical than in human MRSI. For more details about preclinical MRSI, we refer the reader to other review papers [104,106–112].

3. Applications

Despite the above-described challenges, UHF MRSI has already been

successfully applied in a range of studies. This includes pathologies, as well as basic neurosciences. We aim to give a short overview about already realized projects and promising further research.

3.1. Cancer

The potential of 7T MRSI for the diagnosis of neoplasms in the brain, such as gliomas or meningiomas, lies in the option for increased image resolution and better quantification of oncometabolites. The first allows for a better definition of metabolic alterations, possibly beneficial for the presurgical definition of the maximum safe resection volume, which could improve treatment outcome, and the extent of radio- or pharmacotreatment induced changes. The second realizes the imaging of compounds such as glutamine (important for tumor metabolism [113]), glycine (linked to tumor proliferation [114,115]), or 2-hydroxyglutarate (2HG, a product of IDH mutations that correlates with better outcomes [116]), which are more difficult to assess at lower fields, but offer direct information about tumor microenvironments. Historically, most 1.5 and 3 T MRS studies were limited to the evaluation of tCho, tCr and tNAA for tumor grading and extent [117], but 2HG-MRSI has recently become an area of interest [118].

Avdievich et al. demonstrated, for the first time, phase-encoded MRSI in a low-grade glioma in 2009 [119], with a 24×24 matrix (TR = 3s, TE = 15 ms, inversion recovery for lipid suppression, $T_{\text{meas}} = 29$ min), and quantified tNAA, tCr, tCho, myo-inositol (mIns), and lactate. In 2015, Li et al. [94] investigated the use of a 3D-MRSI sequence based on EPSI up to a $20 \times 22 \times 8$ matrix (TR = 2 s, TE =

30 ms, inversion recovery and OVS for lipid suppression, $T_{\text{meas}} = 11$ min) in 29 low- and high-grade gliomas. They found increased ratios of Gln, mIns, glycine (Gly), and glutathione (GSH) to tCr for all tumor grades. In a later comparison between 3 T and 7 T [120], they found more reliable quantification at 7 T, but inversion recovery-based lipid suppression reduced the achievable resolution within the measurement time frame.

FID-MRSI that used a TR of 0.6 s, phase encoding, and parallel imaging was proposed to image gliomas with a 64×64 matrix [121] in 5 min, and was extended by post-acquisition, patch-based, super-resolution in ten patients [122], with imaging of tNAA, tCho, tCr, mIns, Glu, and Gln. This approach was extended with concentric ring trajectories to the acquisition of a $64 \times 64 \times 39$ matrix in 15 min [16] and applied to 23 high-grade glioma patients, resolving heterogeneities in the metabolic images of NAA, tCho, tCr, mIns, Gly, Glu, and Gln [123].

While 2HG was first quantified using single-voxel spectroscopy at 7 T in 2016 [124], in 2018, An et al. introduced an EPSI-based approach for 2HG-optimized MRSI with 78 ms-TE PRESS [125], acquiring a 66×60 matrix in 8 min in five glioma patients (Fig. 3). The detection of 2HG with MRSI was even successfully demonstrated in 18 patients at 9.4T [126]. Beyond proton MRSI, ^{31}P -MRSI at 7 T was used to determine slightly raised inter- and intracellular pH values in gliomas, in a study which was limited to only three patients [127]. ^{31}P -MRSI at 9.4 T found the same trend [128], again limited to three patients.

3.2. Multiple sclerosis

Numerous MRSI studies at lower field strengths (i.e., 1.5 T, 3 T) reported increased mIns, tCho, or decreased NAA, reflecting ongoing reactive gliosis, de-/remyelination, or reduced axonal integrity in various cohorts of multiple sclerosis (MS) patients. However, due to the limited spatial resolution, these studies have focused only on the

normal-appearing WM. The need for a higher resolution for metabolic fingerprinting of relatively small multiple sclerosis lesions was emphasized in two studies at 7 T. In the first, the in-plane voxel dimensions of FID-MRSI were gradually decreased down to $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$, enabling the visualization of WM lesions on spectroscopic images for the very first time [129] (Fig. 4). In the other work, low-resolution metabolic images were upsampled via a patch-based reconstruction method using high-resolution anatomical MR images to regularize the super-resolution process [130], which showed a good match with high-resolution MRSI of MS lesions. FID-MRSI was also utilized to study the metabolic fingerprints of chronic lesions with a hyperintense rim of iron-laden microglia, as seen on susceptibility weighted imaging, as well as T1-hypointense lesions. Iron-rim lesions exhibited gradients of NAA loss across lesion layers and their surroundings, supporting the notion of their slowly expanding nature [131]. In black-hole lesions, T1 relaxation times moderately correlated with the NAA/tCr ratio; however, similarly hypointense lesions exhibited variably increased mIns, which confirmed that such lesions are still metabolically active, and do not represent only scarred tissue [132]. 7 T high-resolution FID-MRSI was also applied to study changes in normal-appearing WM without bias from metabolically more active lesions. Increased mIns, indicative of neuroinflammation, also appeared prior to a decrease of NAA, suggesting it might serve as a biomarker for early pathologic changes, which remain undetected on conventional MRI [133]. Finally, a significant reduction of GSH was reported in the GM and WM lesions of MS patients using spectral-editing PRESS-MRSI at 7 T, demonstrating the potential of this biomarker to probe oxidative stress in MS [7].

3.3. Epilepsy

Compared to the study of gliomas, UHF MRSI of epilepsy still has not received much attention, while the topic of epilepsy itself has been a focus for 7 T MRI [134–136], with three reviews in 2021 alone thus far.

Fig. 3. 2HG-MRSI at 7T based on EPSI with a 2HG-optimized PRESS TE of 78 ms can spectrally separate 2HG and map its spatial distribution. Reproduced with permission from An et al., 2018 [125], *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*.

Fig. 4. 7T FID-MRSI with a single-slice, 100×100 matrix (2.2×2.2 mm² in-plane size) enables visualization of small multiple sclerosis lesions, which cannot be seen with conventional matrix sizes, e.g., 32×32 (6.9×6.9 mm² in-plane size) (A). The metabolic profiles of lesions are also underestimated when using low-resolution MRSI, due to the pronounced partial volume effect from surrounding normal-appearing WM (B).

From MRS at lower fields, we know that epileptogenic regions feature decreased tNAA/tCr [137] and increased tCho/NAA [138]. The first 7 T MRSI study of epilepsy by Pan et al., in 2013 [54] detected decreased tNAA/tCr in hippocampal lesions and could further correlate MRSI findings to post-surgical patient outcomes. As neurotransmitters, Glu and GABA are other neurochemicals of interest, but have been, thus far, investigated only by a single semiLASER-based MRSI study [8] that investigated correlation networks for both. Due to MRSI resolution limitations, Glu in epilepsy has, to date, mostly been investigated using chemical exchange saturation transfer [139,140], but recent advances in UHF high-resolution MRSI [16,123] could allow the mapping of Glu in epilepsy with similar resolutions. A remaining limitation for most UHF-MRSI studies are B0 and B1 inhomogeneities in the basal brain regions that limit the neurochemical imaging of the lower temporal lobe and hippocampus areas, which are of high interest for temporal lobe epilepsy, and specifically, hippocampal sclerosis [141]. GABA alterations in the hippocampus, in particular, merit further investigation [142].

3.4. Hepatic encephalopathy

Hepatic encephalopathy is a brain disorder caused by liver failure which results in an accumulation of toxins in the brain. To date, no MRS (I) study exists about hepatic encephalopathy at UHF. However, at 1.5 T and 3 T several metabolite changes were shown in the brain in animal models, as well as in humans [9]. Specifically, an increase in Gln was consistently found in many studies [143–146], which is most likely caused by increased ammonium concentrations in the brain. Other metabolites such as Glu, Ins, tCho, Tau, tCr and GABA seem to decrease [144–147], partially as a response to the increased osmotic pressure due to the increased Gln. These metabolites have also been shown to be spatially dependent [148]. As a result, UHF scanners in combination with advanced MRSI methodologies and short TE's are very well suited for studying hepatic encephalopathy, especially taking into account the necessity to assess and separate metabolites such as Glu, Gln, Tau and GABA, which can hardly be evaluated at lower field strengths.

3.5. Other neurodegenerative pathologies

UHF MRSI has, as yet, only rarely been used to explore other neurodegenerative pathologies. Hetherington et al. detected significantly decreased NAA (expressed as ratios to tCr and tCho) in the hippocampi of veterans with mild traumatic brain injury using MRSI at 7 T. This work also highlighted the fact that higher-degree shimming at UHF was a critical component that led to improved data quality and likely the overall success of performing spectroscopic imaging in challenging regions, such as the hippocampus [149]. In a subsequent study by this group, NAA/tCho ratios in the hippocampi were correlated with cognitive and neuromotor impairment scores, suggesting that combined

MRSI and neuromotor/cognitive assessment may be useful in monitoring the recovery and effectiveness of interventions [150] after mild traumatic brain injury. 7 T MRSI revealed differences in the neurochemistry of adult X-linked adrenoleukodystrophy, such as increased ml/tCr, tCho/tCr, and decreased NAA/tCr, indicative of astrogliosis, demyelination, and neurodegeneration, which cannot yet be detected on MRI [55].

Three studies were performed at UHF with MRSI based on FID acquisition localized with outer volume suppression (FIDLOVS) in cognitively unimpaired elderly adults, with a potential impact for dementia research. In the work of Quevenoc et al., FIDLOVS MRSI was combined with ¹¹C-Pittsburgh Compound B PET [151]. Preliminary investigation demonstrated that beta-amyloid aggregation is linked to local dysregulation of neuronal inhibition and excitation (expressed via alterations in Glu and GABA). In the second work, Schreiner et al. elucidated the interplay between three typical pathological hallmarks of Alzheimer's disease: amyloid-beta aggregation; cerebrovascular disease; and altered GM neurometabolism (increased mIns/NAA) [152]. Finally, FIDLOVS-MRSI was also applied to study neurometabolic changes associated with low episodic memory performance in the absence of cognitive impairment, which is characteristic of elderly subjects at increased risk for Alzheimer's disease [153].

4. Psychiatric disorders

MRSI in neuropsychiatry has substantially benefited from the high sensitivity of UHFs and improved quantification of extended neurochemical profiles, including abundant neurotransmitters (Glu, Gln, GABA). While neuropsychiatric MRSI studies conducted at lower fields were unable to separate Glu and Gln, and instead, reported their sum Glx [154], this critical limitation of lower fields was overcome at high-field scanners (above 3 T). Glutamate levels were indeed altered in distinct brain regions in schizophrenia and bipolar disorder (BPD), as revealed at 4 T [155] and 7 T [156,157]. Thus, the high and UHF with short TE MRSI methods offer an opportunity to accurately quantify glutamate and glutamine separately [158]. The reliable quantification of Gln at 7 T [16] will enable the study of hepatic encephalopathy, a neuropsychiatric condition where hepatic failure leads to excessive brain glutamine levels [159] and edema [160]. The activity of glutamatergic neurons and Glu/Gln cycling is affected in major depression disorders (MDD) [161] and can be restored by a potent antidepressant and NMDA-Glu receptor antagonist, ketamine [162]. Ketamine modulates the excitatory glutamatergic neurons indirectly via its action on GABAergic neurons in multiple brain regions. An excitatory/inhibitory imbalance (GABA/Glu) also precedes schizophrenia development [163], and plays a role in autism spectrum disorder [164]. As GABA cannot be reliably quantified with MRSI at lower fields [165–167], glutamate/GABA disturbances pose an opportunity for UHF methods [168,169], including 3D approaches available on clinical scanners [170]. Glutamate, together with

lactate, is coupled to oxidative glucose combustion and ATP production. The shift toward cytosolic anaerobic glycolysis is accompanied by increased lactate and attenuated Glu production and occurs due to a compromised glucose oxidative pathway in the mitochondria [171]. Mitochondrial metabolic deficits and the shift from oxidative to anaerobic glucose metabolism [172–174] are considered critical in schizophrenia and BPD pathophysiology [175–177], and thus, need to be reliably quantified using advanced MRSI. Proton MRSI indeed found lactate disturbances in unmedicated BPD patients [157]. Mitochondrial energetic impairment in BPD was linked to Glu alterations in a combined ^1H -MRSI/ ^{31}P -MRSI study in schizophrenia [178] and was demonstrated as an age-dependent decrease of high-energy phosphates with ^{31}P -MRSI [179]. In accord with neurobiological and single-voxel MRS studies [180], MRSI showed NAA, Cho, or Cr deficits in most psychiatric disorders [181]. Although quantification of these singlets is feasible even at lower fields [182], UHF provides improved quantification accuracy and temporal stability [183]. MRSI was also employed in the measurements of treatment responses [184]. A recent 7 T study showed an association between regional alterations in tCho/tCr, NAA/tCr, Glu/tCr, mI/tCr, GABA/tCr, and GSH/tCr in MDD patients with mindfulness-based cognitive therapy and a reduction in depression severity [161]. 3D ^7Li MRSI conducted at 4 T detected uneven Lithium distributions in BPD patients who responded to Lithium therapy [185]. Thus, UHF MRSI can be potentially used for research on individualized pharmacotherapy.

5. Neuroscience

The high sensitivity of UHF allowed accurate measures of ubiquitous neurotransmitters such as Glu and GABA, which maintain the balance between excitation and inhibition and regulate neuronal firing [186]. Thus, UHF MRSI has great potential to extend our comprehension of fundamental and emerging properties of neural circuits. Glu and GABA are involved in memory formation [187], learning of new skills [188], and neural plasticity [189]. Simultaneous mapping of GABA and Glu has been developed at 7 T utilizing spectral editing (Fig. 5). GABA editing methods are sensitive to B0 and B1 fluctuations particularly expressed at UHF, as previously described in this review. These drawbacks have been partially addressed by postprocessing methods [169] and prospective movement correction [190]. GABA editing has been limited to single-slice acquisition at 7 T, and whole-brain coverage constitutes a

future challenge. Glutamate levels respond to physiological and cognitive stimuli, as revealed with MRS methods [191,192]. Functional glutamate responses were ascribed to activated glucose oxidation [193]. Accurate detection of subtle functional responses requires high SNR preserved by ultra-short echo-readouts at UHF scanners. Thus, functional ^1H -MRSI studies have been attempted only with ultra-short echos in mice (2D) [194] and 3D approaches in humans [195] in the barrel and sensorimotor cortex, respectively. Simultaneous mapping of neurochemical information and blood oxygenation level dependent responses utilizing MRSI spectra are another opportunity for 7 T functional ^1H -MRSI. High-energy phosphates relate to the end-stage of oxidative phosphorylation and ATP production. Levels of phosphate compounds were monitored in the visual cortex with 3D ^{31}P -MRSI during an event-related visual stimulation paradigm on a 7 T scanner [196]. Understanding of metabolic variations throughout the normal brain caused by body mass index or sex [197] and metabolic measures during brain development [198] and aging [199–201] are vital for appropriate interpretation of regional metabolic alterations in various diseases. MRSI provides the opportunity to construct brain atlases [202] that show the distribution of brain metabolites and provide normative values, which are currently lacking. Implementation of acceleration techniques allowed for high-resolution images and could access neurochemical information from smaller structures, such as functionally distinct thalamic nuclei [202]. Distinct neurochemical fingerprints reflected different connectivity profiles of thalamic subregions. Novel MRSI UHF methodologies deliver accurate quantification of extended neurochemical profiles and promise to increase our understanding of various mechanisms that alter brain metabolism in health and disease.

5.1. X-nuclear MRSI

X-nuclear MRSI provides a unique window into brain energy metabolism, which relies predominantly on glucose (probed via $^1\text{H}/^2\text{H}$ -MRSI) and oxygen utilization (via ^{17}O -MRSI) to generate biochemical energy in the form of adenosine triphosphate (ATP, via ^{31}P -MRSI [112, 203]). Recent state-of-the-art *in vivo* X-nuclear MRS techniques have shown promise, especially at UHF [204], and are able to improve our understanding of neuroenergetics and brain function in preclinical models and in human subjects under healthy and diseased conditions [203,205]. Biomedical and clinical applications of *in vivo* X-nuclear MRS

Fig. 5. GABA and Glx ratio maps to tNAA acquired with spectral editing-MRSI at 7 T. Reproduced with permission from Moser et al., 2019, *NeuroImage* [168].

face many challenges, with the major limitation of low concentrations of detectable metabolites, low gyromagnetic ratios, and low natural abundance of the detectable nuclei, all of which translates into reduced SNR, and ultimately, relatively poor spatial resolutions compared to ^1H -MRSI (e.g., ~ 1 ml voxel volume and more [112]). One effective way to ameliorate limitations in spatial and chemical specificity (to separate different chemical compounds reliably) is to use UHF MR scanners, which offer significant SNR and spectral resolution improvements [206]. A particular benefit is the feature of X-nuclei sensitivity to increase with B_0 , with a field-strength-dependence that is generally better than a linear relationship and relaxation time properties that are often more favorable for rapid scanning (e.g., ^2H -MRSI [204]). With emerging UHF MR technology now reaching 10.5 T (for human) and 20 T (for animal) research studies, recent technological developments have significantly advanced *in vivo* X-nuclear MRSI and its utility for potential biomedical and clinical applications [207]. *In vivo* MRS/MRSI of nuclei with low gyromagnetic ratios, such as ^2H , ^{13}C , ^{17}O , and ^{31}P , have particularly benefited from this development [208]. Unlike *in vivo* ^1H -MRSI that is handicapped by intense water and lipid contaminations, X-nuclear MRS usually has negligible unwanted background signals, especially at UHF, thus allowing robust 3D imaging of metabolite signals. Another major advantage is that X-nuclear MRSI is generally quite insensitive to inhomogeneities in both the B_0 and B_1 fields. The reasons are that spectral separation of different spectral resonances is typically quite pronounced, even in the presence of B_0 field variation, while standing wave effects that cause B_1 inhomogeneities are a function of the Larmor frequencies, which are lower for all X-nuclei [207]. Still, thus far, human 7T MRSI applications have been limited to ^{31}P and ^2H .

5.1.1. ^{31}P -MRSI

Historically, ^{31}P -MR spectra are the earliest spectra ever reported for MRSI. *In vivo* ^{31}P -MRSI provides a powerful imaging tool for the investigation of brain metabolism and bioenergetics without the use of an isotope-labeled substrate. In addition to ATP, PCr, and Pi molecules, *in vivo* ^{31}P -MRS can also detect other phosphate metabolites, including NAD, and phosphodiester and -monoesters, which are actively involved in oxidative phosphorylation, as well as membrane phospholipid metabolisms. The improvement of spectral resolution at UHF helps to resolve adjacent phosphate metabolite resonances; for instance, NAD+ versus NADH, thus allowing determination of the NAD redox ratio [209–211], as well as separation of intracellular Pi from extracellular Pi, detailed evaluation of phosphomono- and phosphodiester [212], or differentiation of different sugars [213,214] *in vivo*. Finally, it provides improved estimates of important physiological parameters, such as intracellular and extracellular pH [127] and free Mg^{2+} ion concentration in the brain [215]. Using special magnetization (e.g., saturation) transfer techniques, “forward” rate constants and unidirectional fluxes for the creatine kinase reaction and ATPase reaction can be explicitly mapped, demonstrating, for example, significant differences in metabolism between GM and WM.

In the last few years, significant improvements have been achieved in terms of sensitivity by the introduction of advanced RF coil designs [216–218], but also by improved MRSI sequences [219,220]. These have triggered increasing interest in neuro-scientific applications that have previously been strongly SNR-limited, including, for example, studies involving functional X-nuclear MRS [196,221]. While the vast majority of ^{31}P -MRSI studies have been performed at 7 T, a few preliminary, but promising results exist also for 9.4 T [128,222] (Fig. 6). Yet, these reports are mostly limited to the demonstration and feasibility of technological developments.

5.1.2. ^2H -MRSI

^2H is a stable isotope of hydrogen with a spin quantum number of 1 and a very low natural abundance of 0.0156%. The fast T1, but relatively long T2 relaxation, is dominated by the quadrupolar relaxation mechanism that allows rapid signal averaging or MRSI encoding. While

the natural abundance of ^2H is too low for ^2H -MRSI, there is now a trend toward *in vivo* ^2H -MRSI using ^2H -labeled substances; in particular, D-Glucose-6,6-d2 in humans. The main advantages of ^2H -MRSI over ^1H -MRSI, which makes it clinically very attractive, are that it is a very simple and robust method [223], with the ability to label a number of different metabolically active chemical compounds of interest. Additionally, it is relatively cheap compared to positron emission tomography or hyperpolarization, which also allow the assessment of relative metabolic fluxes *in vivo* [224,225]. This could make it a powerful tool for clinical application and research alike [106,223].

Deuterium-labeled substrates, such as glucose, water, and the intermediates of the glycolysis and oxidative pathways including Glx and lactate in the brain tissue can be monitored and identified using their well-resolved resonance signals in dynamic ^2H spectra with excellent sensitivity and temporal resolution. These merits allow for isotope kinetic analysis and eventual quantification of both, the cerebral metabolic rate for glucose consumption and the tricarboxylic acid cycle flux. ^2H -labeled substances can be administered orally or via intravenous infusion, following the successive metabolization through the glycolysis and oxidative phosphorylation pathways. Compared to *in vivo* ^{13}C -MRS, *in vivo* ^2H -MRS has several merits. Very short T1 relaxation times accelerate scanning, spectral patterns and chemical shift assignments similar to those in *in vivo* ^1H -MRS simplify interpretation, and significantly reduced chemical shift displacement artifacts benefit accurate localization. Also, the *in vivo* ^2H signal of naturally abundant water can serve as an internal reference for the absolute quantification of deuterated metabolite concentrations, with no background contamination. In contrast, outer-volume suppression is commonly required in either ^{13}C - or ^1H -MRS to suppress the intense lipid signal or water signal (for ^1H -MRS) contamination. This makes *in vivo* ^2H -MRSI generally more robust, although its relatively poor spectral resolution makes it impossible to resolve the ^2H -labeled Glu and Gln, thus posing a technical challenge for the study of neurotransmission cycling. ^2H -MRSI is valuable for the study of the coupling relationship in the brain between glycolysis and oxidative metabolisms, as well as their impairment in brain disorders, and for the assessment of the Warburg effect in brain tumors [171]. Very recently, dynamic ^2H -to- ^1H exchange label transfer MRSI has been introduced as a potential alternative to direct ^2H -MRSI detection [226]. Both techniques rely on the same administration of ^2H -labeled compounds, but ^2H -to- ^1H -MRSI measures the drop in ^1H -metabolite signal via conventional ^1H -MRSI sequences following the replacement of ^1H with ^2H nuclei during their metabolism. This offers potential advantages of ^1H -MRSI (e.g., better spectral resolution to separate, for example, Glu/Gln or higher SNR), but also shares the disadvantages (e.g., susceptibility to temporal instability/nuisance signals/ B_1 and B_0 inhomogeneities, CSDEs, and SAR requirements) of conventional ^1H -MRSI.

5.1.3. Hyperpolarized ^{13}C -MRSI

Due to the low natural abundance of ^{13}C , and the low gyromagnetic ratio, its signal is very low in comparison to ^1H . The abundance of ^{13}C can be increased by administering ^{13}C -labeled precursors of metabolites, which can then be monitored further downstream in the metabolic pathways. Yet, the SNR is still usually too low for *in-vivo* human brain measurements, which is why hyperpolarization of ^{13}C has been proposed [227,228]. By administering hyperpolarized ^{13}C , the signal can be enhanced by a factor up to 10^5 , although only for a very short time in the order of minutes. To capture as much signal as possible before the T1-decay, very fast MRSI methods like spatio-spectral encoding, compressed sensing and parallel imaging are necessary. Although hyperpolarized ^{13}C -MRSI has never been used at UHF in human brains, the recent applications at 3 T [227–229] are promising, and may pave the way for applications in humans at UHF.

Fig. 6. Concentration estimate maps of PCr, α -ATP, GPC, and PE, as well as intracellular pH maps derived from 9.4 T ^{31}P MRSI. The 3D MRSI acquisition with $6.4 \times 6.7 \times 13.8 \text{ mm}^3$ voxel size took 74 min and was zero-filled to double resolution. Reproduced under the Creative Commons CC by license from Ruhm et al., 2021 [222], *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*.

6. Outlook

The recent clinical approval of 7 T MRI scanners also covers ^{31}P - and ^{23}Na -MRI applications and an extension to ^2H and other nuclei is a relatively small step. This not only accelerates the speed at which new 7T MRI scanners can be installed worldwide, but also opens opportunities to translate advanced UHF ^1H and X-nuclear MRSI-based neuro-metabolic imaging techniques to more clinical research applications, such as diagnosis and monitoring treatment efficacy.

Despite significant advancement in MRSI technology at UHF, its spatiotemporal resolution with the current state-of-the-art UHF technology is still limited for some brain applications, particularly for X-nuclear MRSI. Further improvements to boost MRSI sensitivity and spatiotemporal resolution could be achieved via recent developments in hardware and software technology.

A particularly promising technology is that of multi-channel B0 shim coils, which are expected to have a much larger impact on MRSI than on single-voxel MRS. This will have a significant impact on both spectral resolution and nuisance signal suppression in challenging brain regions, consequently making MRSI (^1H -MRSI in particular) more robust. Apart from this, most currently available X-nuclear coils are relatively simple and more advanced multi-channel RF coil designs will offer significant boosts in SNR.

The significant technical advantages associated with direct FID-MRSI will likely dominate future sequence developments in both ^1H - and X-nuclear MRSI. However, further improvements in faster and automated data processing and more robust, especially software-based, nuisance signal suppression, will be critical. It is expected that new developments in MRSI will continue to integrate further spatial and spectral prior knowledge. Techniques such as SPectroscopic Imaging by exploiting spatioSpectral Correlation (SPICE) [97], which use the unique property of the low-rankedness of spectroscopic signals to enable special data acquisition, and image reconstruction strategies to obtain high-resolution spatioSpectral distributions, as well as high temporal resolution, will become more common. Thus far, SPICE and similar low-rank-based approaches have been mainly shown for 3 T, where nuisance signal suppression is more robust. However, after overcoming these limitations, the incorporation of these novel techniques at UHF could break the current technical barriers and significantly advance MRSI. Especially *in vivo* X-nuclear-MRSI could benefit much earlier from the use of additional spatioSpectral prior knowledge, where nuisance signals are far less of an issue than for ^1H -MRSI. A very new field with high potential is that of advanced machine-learning in MRSI reconstruction [81,230], processing, and analysis, and future developments are thus difficult to predict.

Further research efforts will also involve the development of more realistic models for the determination of physiology parameters of interest, such as metabolic fluxes. Particularly in relatively new research fields, such as dynamic *in vivo* ^2H -MRSI of ^2H -labeled compounds [106, 231], the experience with retrieving quantitative measures of metabolic fluxes for complex metabolic pathways is still quite limited. Also, the ^2H -labeling of new substrates will be certainly investigated in future studies and the array of possible applications will expand beyond early proof-of-principle studies in brain tumors and the investigation of liver and brain tissues.

In addition to innovative new ways to map healthy and pathological tissue metabolism, imaging neurotransmitters such as Glu and GABA (possibly functionally) has many potential applications for neuroscience and our understanding of human brain networks, as well as their disruption by neurological or psychiatric diseases. Directly measuring the effects of new pharmaceuticals on neurotransmitters is an exciting field of application for UHF MRSI. Utilizing the spectral resolution possible at UHFs, separating, e.g., Gln from Glu, allows insight into additional biochemical changes that could even be caused by diseases outside the brain, such as hepatic encephalopathy [9].

Nevertheless, ultimately, before any of these techniques can find

widespread use, they will require the support of the MRI manufacturers to enable the production of easy-to-use hardware/software solutions that are accessible to non-expert users. We conclude that the great progress achieved with UHF MRSI, despite all its current limitations, has brought the community closer to this point, hopefully accelerating the spread of MRSI as a useful application for research and for clinical indications.

Declaration of interest

All authors have no financial interests to declare.

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